

Building a Case Study of Cimaragas Village in the Ciamis Regency Using the Village Index

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ABSTRACT: This study investigates the development issues faced by the government in light of the Village Development Index, which measures the degree of village independence based on social, economic, and environmental factors as a map of village development. The research area for examining how the Village Law on village development is being implemented is Cimaragas Village, Cimaragas Subdistrict, and Ciamis Regency. By searching for data sources from the study of literature and related paperwork, this research was carried out in a qualitative descriptive manner. According to the study's findings, based on the villages' updated Village Building Index for the years 2018 to 2022, there is an improvement in the status of village independence. When development is carried out in a village in line with the law, but the development objectives are not met and village governance negatively impacts development, this situation is not ideal.

KEYWORDS: Village Development, Village Development Index

1. INTRODUCTION

The laws and regulations governing villages provide new planning and mechanisms for village development, where the village becomes an actor in development. According to PP number 6 of 2014 concerning Villages, "Villages are villages and traditional villages or what is called by another name, hereinafter referred to as Village, is a legal community unit that has territorial boundaries that are authorized to regulate and manage government affairs, the interests of the local community based on community initiatives, rights of origin, and/or traditional rights that are recognized and respected in the system of government of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia". So village development can be interpreted as an effort by the government to create a prosperous village community in meeting the needs of life and optimizing the potential of the village for the utilization of village community empowerment in carrying out economic activities and utilizing the sustainable environment. The creation of the Village Law regulations strengthens the position of the Village by providing an affirmation of Village finances which includes village-scale local authority and origin rights authority. With this authority, the village has full rights to manage development on the basis of village deliberation as the highest decision holder. Community participation is the key to advancing the village towards an Independent Village. Village development itself includes the stages of planning, implementation, supervision and accountability based on Permendagri 114/2014 concerning Village Development Guidelines. To determine the target locus for the alleviation of Disadvantaged Villages, the government developed the Developing Village Index (IDM) which became a map for the development of village development. The IDM consists of the Social Resilience Index (IKS); Economic Resilience Index (IKE); and the Environmental Resilience Index (IKL). in line with the concept of sustainable development, namely development that includes social, economic, and environmentally sustainable dimensions. Based on the assessment of field conditions according to the indicators of each index, it produces progress status and results

Village independence consisting of Independent Villages, Advanced Villages, Developing Villages, Disadvantaged Villages and Very Disadvantaged Villages. The classification is an affirmation of the village's independence status and the interventions that need to be given. Cimaragas Village is one of the villages in Cimaragas District, Ciamis Regency, which consists of 5 hamlets namely Sukahayu Hamlet, Cimaragas Hamlet, Rancagede Hamlet, Sarirahayu Hamlet, and Cimaragas Village is located south of the Citanduy River and north of the Cimaragas River and to the west of Situ Batu Village, Banjar District and East of Beber Village, Cimaragas District with a geographic area of 616,395 Ha, where the area is mostly used for agriculture. From this condition, it can be seen that agriculture is the biggest potential possessed by Independent Villages based on the Developing Village Index (IDM).

The following is the value of the Cimaragas Village Building Village Index (IDM) for 2018-2022, based on the Decree of the Director General of PPMD Kemendes PDTT.

Table 1.

Year	IKS	IKE	IKL	IDM	Status
2018	0.7337	0.7337	0.7337	0.7337	Berkembang
2019	0.8274	0.6766	0.5733	0.6925	Berkembang
2020	N/A	N/A	N/A	0.6930	Berkembang
2021	N/A	N/A	N/A	0.6974	Berkembang
2022	0.8629	0.8167	0.8667	0.8487	Mandiri

From table 1, we can see that Cimaragas Village continues to experience growth in the IDM value of 0.1562 in 2019 to 2022. This increase in the index causes the status of Cimaragas Village to increase from a Developing Village to an independent village in 2022. Despite an increase in the resilience aspect economic, social and environmental, the unavailability of data for 2020 and 2021 is a problem that needs to be questioned. The increase in the value of the Developing Village Index shows the growth in the quality of economic, environmental and social fulfillment. This increase is influenced by the implementation of development according to its authority. As research conducted by Muhtarom, et al (2018), that the activities carried out by the village have an influence on changes in the IDM composite index value.

As a village that has natural tourism potential and agricultural potential, the increase in this index shows progress with the village development goals as mentioned. Development is a conscious and continuous process of change to achieve progress and improvement of a better life towards the desired goal, so that In development, there are elements of change, goals, and potential by providing opportunities for community aspirations to find a middle point to achieve common goals (Agus Suryono, 2010). The potential possessed by the village is managed to support the achievement of village development goals (Bakti, 2018). In addition, village governance and community participation also have an influence on the development and improvement of village community life (Setyowati, 2019).

According to Tay and Rusmiwari (2019), there are supporting and inhibiting factors in implementing sustainable development in villages. Supporting factors include the availability of abundant natural resources, and qualified human resources in the field of development; the existence of legal certainty or regulations governing sustainable development policies; and a high level of community participation and public awareness of the importance of development. While the inhibiting factors include the lack of insight and mindset about the importance of sustainable development, lack of community participation, natural phenomena that hinder infrastructure development, as well as the pros and cons of the community that hinder the village government in making decisions.

For this reason, this study will attempt to explain the stages of development implementation in Cimaragas Village, Cimaragas District, Ciamis Regency whose IDM value continues to increase, to determine the supporting and inhibiting factors of development in Cimaragas Village and the impact of implementing development in Cimaragas Village on the achievement of development goals and objectives. evaluate it with the dimensions of consistency, transparency, accountability, fairness, participatory, effectiveness and efficiency (Ramdhani, 2016).

2. METHOD

This study examines the development of village development in the Cimaragas sub-district, Cimaragas village by looking at the index of developing villages by collecting data from various literatures and references as well as from various previous studies that have been carried out. In addition, data were obtained from agencies related to this research.

3. RESULT & DISCUSSION

The implementation of Village Development in Cimaragas Village is guided by the Minister of Home Affairs Regulation concerning Village Development Guidelines. The stages of implementing village development carried out by Cimaragas Village include the stages of Compiling the Village RPJM, Compiling the Village RKP, Preparation of the Village APB, Implementation of the Village APB/Village Development, Accountability for the Implementation of Village Development. The preparation of the Cimaragas Village RPJM 2019-2024, the stages carried out by Cimaragas Village are as follows: 1) Meeting for the formation of

the RPJM-Des Drafting Team attended by elements of LPM/LKMD, LK, Village PKK, KPM, Community Leaders, Religious Leaders and so on. The team is determined by a decree on the formation of the RPJM-DES Preparation Team. 2) The drafting of the DES RPJM is carried out internally by the Drafting Team .3) The Village Deliberation discusses and determines the Draft RPJM-Des that has been made by the Drafting Team.

From this condition, we can see that the process of compiling the RPJM DES of Cimaragas Village for 2019-2024 is in accordance with the laws and regulations. The existing Document Archives, supported by statements from BPD members and their assistants, show that the RPJM-Desa Cimaragas is optimally prepared with several stages of completion. Based on the archive of documents for the preparation of the RKP Cimaragas Village, it has been compiled through the Musdes related to the scrutiny of the RPJMDes then followed by the mechanism of the Village Development Planning Deliberation (Musrenbangdes) related to the approval of the RKPDes Draft and stipulated by the Village Regulation on the Village Government Work Plan every month of each year.

After the RKP of Cimaragas Village is determined by Perdes, the Cimaragas Village Government prepares the Penatahan Village Revenue and Expenditure Budget in accordance with the budget ceiling and activities in the agreed RKPDesa. The draft APBDesa Cimaragas is inputted into the SISKEUDES application which is officially managed by the Ministry of Home Affairs. The results of the input to SISKEUDES are evaluated by the Cimaragas sub-district head in coordination with the Community and Village Empowerment Office of Ciamis Regency. Once approved, the APB Cimaragas Village is determined by the Cimaragas Village Regulation concerning the Cimaragas Village Revenue and Expenditure Budget every year. This is in accordance with the rules set by the government. The implementation of village development in Cimaragas Village is more in the development of village infrastructure. This condition is shown in the realization of APBDesa Cimaragas expenditure from 2018 where the largest expenditure is in the field of development implementation.

Table 2. Realization of Cimaragas Village Expenditures in 2018-2021

Year	The Field of Administration	Village Development Implementation Sector	Field of Community Development	Field of Community Empowerment
2018	569.003.476,	1.093.742.000,	21.936.000,	83.377.500
2019	979.080.024,	1.240.383.000,	72.803.000,	10.058.000
2020	635.516.561,	923.240.400,00	72.837.000,	N/A
2021	61.015.553,	981.161.960,00	55.621.000,	44.371.000

Source: Cimaragas Village Accountability Report 2018-2021

From table 2, we can see that the focus of the implementation of Cimaragas Village development from 2018 to 2021 is still on the development of village facilities and infrastructure. Budget support for community institutions in Cimaragas Village increased in 2019 and 2020, then decreased in 2021. As for the field of community empowerment, it continued to decrease from 2018, 2019, and increased in 2021.

The Village Build Index assesses village independence based on the concept of sustainable development, namely from the social, economic and environmental aspects of sustainability. The development carried out by Cimaragas Village from 2018 to 2021 is more focused on the development of village infrastructure so that the condition of basic rural social infrastructure in Cimaragas Village which includes health services, access to education, public facilities, settlement facilities is getting better and supports increasing value. Penatahan Village Social Resilience Index. The low budget for community empowerment which is used to improve the community's ability to meet their daily needs has an influence on the decline in the Cimaragas Village Economic Resilience Index.

Utilization of potential to achieve development goals is not carried out in Cimaragas Village. Agriculture as the biggest potential of Cimaragas Village has been slightly touched by the 2018 to 2020 development budget. In relation to ecology, in the 2018 to 2021 Pemahatan Village Budget, there is no budget to support the environment. Until now, Cimaragas Village does not have a waste management site. This has an influence on the decrease in the value of the Cimaragas Village Environmental Resilience Index. In carrying out village development, Cimaragas Village has factors that hinder and support the implementation of development. The inhibiting factors consist of: 1. Weaknesses in data documentation. 2. The limited budget cannot meet all development needs. 3. Low level of participation. 4. Sub-optimal village governance.

While the supporting factors are good relations between the village government and the BPD to facilitate the process of determining village development documents including the Village RPJM Document, Village Regulations concerning RKP Villages, Village Regulations concerning APBDesa, and Village Regulations concerning Accountability for Implementation of APBDesa although the process is inconsistent with respect to the Village Budget. applicable laws and regulations. This causes no obstacles in the preparation and implementation of the Village Budget. Cimaragas Village has a vision of "Cimaragas Bengras" Village. To realize this vision, the Village RPJM, RKPDesa and APBDesa are prepared. This Social Resilience Index is an indicator of the success of achieving the mission of Cimaragas Village to be friendly and in serving the community and to be synergistic and harmonious with all stakeholders.

In the 2019-2021 village independence status update, the value of the Cimaragas Village Social Resilience Index increased from 0.7337 (2018) to 0.8274 (2019). This increase indicates an improvement in the quality of health services, access to education, housing infrastructure, and social capital (solidarity, tolerance, security, public space, social welfare). In line with the development focus on the Cimaragas Village Budget from 2018 to 2021, the dominant budget is for the implementation of the construction of basic rural social facilities.

The Economic Resilience Index is an indicator of the vision of a Prosperous Cimaragas Village through a creative economy. The activities of the APBDesa that touch the creative economy are to realize the capital investment of BUMDes with a budget of Rp. 67,946,000, - in the formation in 2018. The steps to increase the economy by the village government have not touched the greatest potential of Cimaragas village. Of the 196.03 Ha area of Cimaragas Village, 70 Ha is agricultural land and 29 Ha is dry land and 97 Ha is public facilities.

Supported by most of the livelihoods of the residents of Cimaragas Village as farmers (970 men and 275 women from 1,998 working groups). This condition is in line with the decline in the value of the Economic Resilience Index in the 2018 and 2019 updates, the Environmental Resilience Index is an indicator that is less attention to its success for the vision of Cimaragas Brenghas Cimaragas Village itself does not have waste management facilities so it depends on each household. This condition is in line with the decline in the value of the Penatahan Village Environmental Resilience Index in the 2018 and 2019 updates.

The Village Development Index does not measure the implementation of Village governance so that the success of Cimaragas' goals related to improving the quality of village governance cannot be measured by the Village Building Index. The steps that have been taken are to carry out activities to increase the capacity of village government officials and BPD every year. By increasing the capacity of village government apparatus, the implementation of development from the planning, implementation and accountability stages should run according to the rules. However, from the document archives, it was found that the implementation did not comply with the rules, such as village meetings that did not involve community elements in accountability village meetings, the determination of Village Regulations regarding RKPDesa that exceeded the time limit.

From the accountability report of the Cimaragas APBDesa every year, on physical project work such as road and building construction, there should be an efficiency in the material budget resulting from procurement negotiations, but the budget is realized without any budget efficiency. The Village Development Index does not consider the dimensions of village governance and the existence of Village Original Income in determining the level of Village independence. In this study, village governance in Penatahan Village which in the process there are stages that are not in accordance with laws and regulations affects development due to low community participation in the process of implementing village development. Likewise, in the absence of Village Original Income, development activities in Penatahan Village depend on the budget provided by the central, provincial and district governments, so that budget shortfalls to achieve the vision, mission, goals, and policy directions cannot be avoided.

The village development policies that have been implemented by Cimaragas Village in 2016-2021 have been implemented and have an influence on the achievement of Cimaragas Village goals. The implementation of the development needs to be evaluated so that it can be used as a reference for improvement and improvement in order to optimize the achievement of development goals. The results of the evaluation carried out based on the evaluation dimensions according to Ramdhani (2016) are as follows:

Transparency, Transparency of village development is still only in the form of installing billboards containing information on the general description of the Village Budget. Involving the community in village deliberation and village development planning deliberation which is a form of transparency in village development planning is not carried out in Cimaragas Village. So it can be said that the transparency of the implementation of development in the village is still lacking.

Accountability The implementation of village development in Penatahan Village is accounted for at the beginning of each year in the following fiscal year through the village deliberation mechanism. However, the village deliberations carried out did not involve elements of community representatives so that there were no stages of accountability for the implementation of development to the community. Participatory, the condition of the implementation of village deliberations and village development planning deliberations that are less active, seem formality and do not involve community elements, indicate low participation in the implementation of village development in Cimaragas Village.

Based on the Developing Village Index which consists of three aspects, namely social, economic and environmental, seen from the IKS aspect, the use of APBDesa for the construction of basic rural infrastructure is efficient in increasing the IKS value in the 2018 and 2019 updates significantly. Meanwhile, viewed from the economic and environmental aspects, the budget used for economic and environmental improvement activities is inefficient because in the 2018 and 2019 updates the IKE and IKL values have decreased. The Penatahan Village Government has invested in BUMDes but in three years the management of BUMDes has not been able to provide Village Original Income, so this capital participation can be notarized as not efficient.

3. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research and discussion of the focus of the problem in this study, then the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Cimaragas Village has carried out the stages of implementing Village development but not in accordance with the provisions of the legislation.
2. Village development carried out in Cimaragas Village has an influence on the achievement of village development goals as stated in the vision, mission, goals and policy directions of Penatahan Village development.
3. Village governance in Cimaragas Village which is not in accordance with the laws and regulations has an influence on development due to low community participation. This is not taken into account in the Village Building Index in determining the level of village independence.
4. The absence of Village Original Income in Cimaragas Village causes dependence on the budget provided by the central, provincial and district governments so that there are policy directions that are not supported by activities to be achieved. This is not taken into account in the Village Building Index in determining the level of village independence. Based on the results of this study, researchers can provide the following suggestions: 1. Preparation of village development planning documents which include Village RPJM, Village RKP, Village Budgets, so that they are in accordance with applicable laws and regulations, in terms of the stages passed, implementation time, and stakeholders involved. involved. Transparency of information is important to increase public participation. Community involvement from the planning, implementation, monitoring and accountability stages is important to improve, by inviting community elements in village meetings and village development planning meetings. 2. The Village Government needs to optimize agricultural potential, both from the APBDesa budget or the BUMDes business. This needs to be done so that farmers no longer sell agricultural products to middlemen, so that farmers' income from selling agricultural products is maximized. BUMDes that serve the distribution of BPNT can take rice from farmers in Penatahan Village so that farmers get the selling price they should. 3. The central government should develop the Village Build Index by considering the dimensions of village governance and the existence of Village Original Income in determining the level of Village independence

AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTIONS

The title "AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTIONS" should be in all caps.

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